

STRUCTURAL AND MICROSCOPY CHARACTERIZATION OF AN ALTERNATIVE LOW-ENERGY BINDER CONTAINING $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ AS AN ALKALINE ACTIVATOR

Aditianto Ramelan
Doctor of Engineering*

Adhi Setyo Nugroho
Corresponding author

Bachelor of Engineering*
E-mail: adhisnugroho37@gmail.com

Teti Indriati
Master of Engineering
Department of Mining Engineering**

Riska Rachmanty
Master of Engineering*

*Department of Materials Science
and Engineering**

Bandung Institute of Technology
Ganesha str., 10, Bandung, Indonesia, 40132

The development of potential alternative binders to Portland cement is still becoming a global challenge in housing and infrastructure aspects. That is because cement and concrete becomes the major materials needed in building constructions. The Ordinary Portland cement can form a solid and hard mass when mixed with water with a certain ratio. This is due to the formation of ettringite and calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) phases that contribute to the strength of the hydrated products about 33–53 MPa. However, the manufacturing temperature of Portland cement can reach up to 1,500 °C in producing clinker. In order to lower the energy consumption and production cost, scientists were trying to utilize pozzolanic materials.

The research of pozzolanic materials as alkali-activated cement, such as soil cement or geopolymer cement, is also still conducted. Hence, a better understanding of pozzolanic reaction and its hydration products is needed. In this work, the hydration products of low-energy binders composed of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-metakaolin-gypsum}$ mixtures were studied.

The hydrated products of 41 wt. % $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ – 41 wt. % metakaolin – 18 wt. % gypsum mixtures followed by water immersion curing at 50 °C for 28 days undergone a pozzolanic reaction. XRD characterization showed that the hydrated product is mainly composed of ettringite (60.0 %) and crystalline-CSH (23.4 %). The diffractograms obtained have shown a specific hump indicating the presence of amorphous phases besides the crystalline. To confirm the presence of the non-crystalline or amorphous phases of the hydrated products, a polarizing optical microscope (OM) using a crossed Nicols method was used. The characterization of the phases is the novelty of the present research. The ettringite, crystalline CSH and the amorphous phases act as a strong binder that consequently contribute to its average maximum compressive strength of 22.17 MPa

Keywords: low-energy binder, alkaline activator, metakaolin, pozzolanic reaction, diffractogram hump, amorphous phase, polarised optical microscope

Received date: 21.04.2021

How to Cite: Ramelan, A., Nugroho, A. S., Indriati, T., Rachmanty, R. (2021). Structural and microscopy characterization of an alternatively low energy binder containing $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as an alkaline activator. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*,

Accepted date: 26.05.2021

3 (6 (111)), 71–79. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2021.233182>

Published date: 18.06.2021

1. Introduction

Portland cement production with a firing process in a rotary kiln requires a clinkering temperature of up to 1,500 °C [1, 2]. It consumes a large amount of energy and produces highly carbon dioxide emissions [3]. In addition, the firing process also produces fine-powdered silica dust that can cause respiratory disturbances of silicosis [4]. Thus, the focus of the present cement industry is to find an alternative method to reduce the energy consumption during the manufacturing process of cement powder in order to save the production costs and environment, while producing high-quality products [1, 5]. One such alternative is by utilizing alkali-activated cements through the role of pozzolanic materials. Pozzolanic materials generally consist of aluminosilicates, which have alkali-reactive properties, are eco-friendly, and require low energy consumptions [6, 7]. Among them are metakaolin, fly ash, silica fume, blast furnace slag, etc. The pozzolanic reaction occurs when the reactive pozzolanic materials are activated by using alkaline solutions, such as alkali hydroxides, i.e. sodium hydroxide (NaOH) or calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), and alkali sulphates [5]. The reaction

between pozzolanic materials and alkaline solution with the presence of water will cause the formation of the hard, solid, and compact body, thus it is called a hydraulic binder.

Actually, viewed from the historical milestones, the principle of the hydraulic binder using alkali-activated aluminosilicate materials was firstly found by Glukhovskiy in the late 1950s. He called that binder as “soil cements”. Later, Krivenko called it as “geocements”, while Davidovits termed it as “geopolymer” because it has a polymer-like structure [5]. Up to now, scientists are still developing the possibility of using alkali-activated cements as an alternative to Portland cement due to the low energy consumption and production costs. One of the potential candidates is by using fine-powdered silica and metakaolin as the pozzolanic materials, with calcium hydroxides as the alkaline activator.

2. Literature review and problem statement

Portland cement is manufactured by calcining three main materials such as limestone (CaCO_3), silica sand (SiO_2), and

clay ($x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot y\text{SiO}_2 \cdot z\text{H}_2\text{O}$) with suitable chemical compositions at about 1,500 °C in a rotary kiln machine. The materials are melted, mixed, and then cooled as clinkers. After that, the clinkers are mixed again with the gypsum chunks and ground in a ball mill machine to obtain the finely powdered cement [1, 2].

Portland cement is also one of the hydraulic binders because it can harden and form a solid body after mixed with water at a room temperature with a certain water/cement ratio. The reaction is called a hydration reaction. Portland cement powder contains some important phases that contribute to the hydration reaction, namely alite ($3\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2$), belite ($2\text{CaO} \cdot \text{SiO}_2$), aluminate ($3\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$), ferrite ($4\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), and the additional gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) powder as a set retarder and a strength accelerator [2, 8]. The products of hydration reaction mainly consist of calcium silicate hydrate (CSH), ettringite or calcium aluminosilicate hydrate (CASH), calcium aluminohydrate (CAH), and calcium hydroxide (CH or $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) [2, 6].

The issue of studying alkali-activated cements has remained relevant and important. Alkali-activated cements using pozzolanic materials and alkaline activators undergo hydration reaction, as well as the Portland cement. In addition, specifically, they also undergo a pozzolanic reaction. The papers [6, 9] state that the hydration products of the pozzolanic materials reacted with alkaline solution are CSH, ettringite, and CAH. From this standpoint, the alkali-activated cement using pozzolanic materials probably has similarity with Portland cement in terms of chemical reaction mechanism, reaction products, and mechanical properties of the hydrated products.

Based on the American Concrete Institute (ACI CT-13), pozzolanic materials are defined as a siliceous or silico-aluminous material, which in fine form can chemically react with calcium hydroxide and water at room temperature to form compounds having cementitious properties. The pozzolanic reaction produces a CSH phase that contributes to the long-term strength of the hydrated products [10].

Metakaolin (MK), $x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot y\text{SiO}_2$, is one example of the pozzolanic materials that can be obtained from the calcination of kaolinite clay ($x\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot y\text{SiO}_2 \cdot z\text{H}_2\text{O}$) at the elevated temperature of about 750–900 °C [4, 11]. It is usually added into blended Portland cements as supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) due to its special properties. The paper [11] shows that metakaolin improves the workability of the cement paste, increases the setting time of the concrete by 10 % addition, and also enhances the compressive strength of the concrete. The high reactivity of metakaolin may increase the heat of hydration and accelerates the hydration reaction of the cement paste, resulting in a faster setting time. The paper [6] states that the structure of penta-coordinated aluminum ions makes metakaolin very reactive, and in its fine form in the cement paste it consumes portlandite or calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) producing CSH and CAH binding phases. While the reaction of the Al_2O_3 site with gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in aqueous solutions will produce an ettringite phase, which contributes to the initial strength of the concrete structure [8, 12]. The paper [13] also shows that the addition of 15 % metakaolin to the cement composition possibly prevents destructive processes in concrete exposed in a high alkali content environment.

Geopolymer cement is one of the alkali-activated cements that use the reaction between metakaolin as pozzolanic material and NaOH as alkaline activator, resulting in

the polymer-like binding structure of sodium aluminosilicate hydrate (NASH). Meanwhile, besides NaOH, the paper [14] suggests that $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ can also be used as another alkaline activator for metakaolin. Thus, Zemlicka et. al [6] presented the research of the hydration reaction products of metakaolin- $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and metakaolin- $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ -gypsum mixtures. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) methods showed the presence of ettringite and CSH phases. But, there was an unresolved issue related to the characterization of the amorphous phase of the hydrated products. The reason for this may be the objective difficulty associated with the suitable method chosen, which makes relevant research impractical. However, in studying an alternative binder to Portland cement, it is also important to understand and distinguish the crystalline and amorphous structures that mainly contribute to the strength of the products. A way to overcome this difficulty can be through a conventional petrographic examination. The papers [15, 16] state that conventional petrographic examination using a polarising optical microscope (OM) is commonly used as a quick method in characterizing the amorphous phase of cementitious materials.

Polarising OM is the simplest way to overcome this difficulty in observing the amorphous phase structure. The methods used are parallel nicols and crossed nicols by adjusting the analyzer and polarizer. The observed light will behave depending on the structure of the materials. By using both parallel nicols and crossed nicols, if the observed light passing through the specimen shows a variety of colors, then the materials can be classified as anisotropic, e.g. silica, portlandite, and kaolinite. While by using crossed nicols, if the observed light passing through the specimen shows only dark color, then the materials can be classified as isotropic, e.g. diamond, glass, and amorphous solids.

All this suggests that it is advisable to design alternative binder mixtures to Portland cement. In this work, the idea is taken from the secondary pozzolanic reaction on a high-strength concrete of which $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as a product of the primary hydration process reacts usually with reactive SiO_2 resulting in a secondary CSH phase or called as CSH_2 .

The production of the CSH_2 product from the secondary hydration or the pozzolanic reaction was an interesting phenomenon to observe.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the study is the development of the low-energy binder composed of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ - SiO_2 and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ -metakaolin-gypsum mixtures without the addition of Portland or any other conventional cement products. This will make it possible to obtain the hydrated products with the compressive strength not below 20 MPa at 28 days.

To achieve the aim, the following objectives have been set:

- to determine the compressive strength of hydrated products of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ - SiO_2 and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ - SiO_2 mixtures with CaO and metakaolin addition;
- to determine the compressive strength development of the hydrated products of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ -metakaolin-gypsum mixtures;

- to qualitatively and semi-quantitatively identify the phases that appeared in the selected mixtures with the relatively highest compressive strength value due to its treatment;
- to confirm the presence of amorphous phases that contribute to the strength development using a polarizing optical microscope following the humps shown in the diffractograms.

4. Materials and methods

The $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ system was used as the initial experimental base, by using $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as an alkaline activator and fine-powdered silica as pozzolanic material. The materials used in this work are as follows. Limestone was obtained from Padalarang, Bandung, Indonesia. It was then burned at a temperature of 1100°C for one hour. The burned limestone was left in the open air for a week in order to obtain $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ powder. Silica powder, SiO_2 (SikaFume, Indonesia) with a grain size of about 0.75 microns or passed 200-mesh sieve. White kaolin powder (Bolus Alba, Bandung, Indonesia) and gypsum powder (Bratachem, Bandung, Indonesia). The white kaolin was burned at a temperature of 750°C for two hours to convert the kaolin into a metakaolin phase [4].

There were two mixtures used in this work: $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-metakaolin-gypsum}$ mixtures as shown in Table 1. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and SiO_2 were mixed in a weight ratio $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{SiO}_2$ of 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 1.0. They were mixed with water using a water/solid ratio of 0.3. After that, they were cast into a $5\times 5\times 5$ cm cube mold to form specimens for compressive strength test after 14, 21, and 28 days of curing. The curing method used was atmospheric curing and the specimen demoulding process was done after 6–7 days of casting. We also applied some modification to $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ mixtures. The CaO and metakaolin were added into the mixtures, as simply shown in Table 1. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, metakaolin, and gypsum were mixed with a composition of 41 wt. % $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ – 41 wt. % metakaolin – 18 wt. % gypsum according to the work of Zemlicka et.al [6]. They were mixed with water using a water/solid ratio of 0.7. Then, they were cast into a $5\times 5\times 5$ cm cube mold for compressive strength test specimens with ages of 3, 7, 14, and 28 days. After 2 days of casting, the specimens were demoulded for the curing process. The curing method used was immersed in the water and it was performed at a temperature of 50°C and 20°C . The water immersed curing method was used to get the most effective result, i.e. the highest result in compressive strength.

Compressive tests of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-metakaolin-gypsum}$ specimens were performed by using a TarnoGrocki compression machine with a load cell of 50–200 kN and a load speed of 0.7 mm/min.

Metakaolin and the specimens with the highest compressive strength were used for XRD characterization. Those three samples are CH-MK-G-50, CH-MK-G-20, and CH-15MK/S. Samples CH-MK-G-50 and CH-MK-G-20 were characterized by using Shimadzu XRD-7000 Maxima type diffractometer operating at 40 kV–30 mA and using

$\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. While metakaolin and CH-15MK/S samples were characterized by using Philips XPert MPD type diffractometer operating at 40 kV–30 mA and using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. The diffractograms were analyzed qualitatively to identify the phases. While CH-MK-G-50 and CH-MK-G-20 were also analyzed semi-quantitatively to determine their phase compositions by using X Powder™ software with PDF2 database.

The petrographic examination of samples CH-MK-G-50 and CH-MK-G-20 was done using two kinds of polarizing OM. Both samples were in the form of thin sections with about 30 microns thickness. The presence of the amorphous phase was observed by using conventional polarizing OM supported by a LED lamp as a light source to obtain the best lighting. Samsung J7-6 rear camera was used to take about 5–8 images for each sample observed in the crossed nicols mode. While the other phases and aggregates were observed by using Nikon digital polarizing OM with both parallel nicols and crossed nicols methods. All the images were processed by using ImageJ software to adjust the image brightness and/or sharpness.

Table 1

Compositions of the mixtures and their curing process

No.	Sample code	Mixture Compositions	w/s ratio	Curing method	Curing time (days)
1	CH/S-0.2	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{SiO}_2=0.2$	0.3	Atmospheric curing	14, 21, 28
	CH/S-0.4	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{SiO}_2=0.4$			
	CH/S-0.6	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{SiO}_2=0.6$			
	CH/S-1.0	$\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{SiO}_2=1.0$			
2	CH-5C/S	$[\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2+5 \text{ wt. \% CaO}]/\text{SiO}_2=1.0$	0.3	Atmospheric curing	14
	CH-10C/S	$[\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2+10 \text{ wt. \% CaO}]/\text{SiO}_2=1.0$			
	CH-15C/S	$[\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2+15 \text{ wt. \% CaO}]/\text{SiO}_2=1.0$			
	CH-5MK/S	$[\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2+5 \text{ wt. \% metakaolin}]/\text{SiO}_2=1.0$	0.3	Atmospheric curing	14
	CH-10MK/S	$[\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2+\text{wt. \% metakaolin}]/\text{SiO}_2=1.0$			
	CH-15MK/S	$[\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2+15 \text{ wt. \% metakaolin}]/\text{SiO}_2=1.0$			
3	CH-MK-G-50	41 wt. % $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ – 41 wt. % metakaolin – 18 wt. % gypsum	0.7	Immersed in water; $T=50^\circ\text{C}$	3, 7, 14, 28
	CH-MK-G-20			Immersed in water; $T=20^\circ\text{C}$	

5. Research results of testing and characterization of alternative low-energy binders

5.1. Compressive strength of the $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ hydrated products

Fig. 1 shows an increase in the compressive strength of the hydrated products along with the addition of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ (higher $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2/\text{SiO}_2$ or CH/S) from 14 until 28 days of atmospheric curing. It means that the mixture has the ability to form a solid mass with low binding or cementing properties because the compressive strength of the materials is still less than 1 MPa. In this case, it should be noted that the mixture does not undergo a pozzolanic reaction. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ acts as a binder and SiO_2 acts as a filler or aggregate, and they exhibit only adhesion bonding. Thus, for CH/S=0.2 and

CH/S=0.6, as the CH/S ratio increases with the curing time, the more the cementing ability of the binder, the higher the compressive strength of the hydrated products. While for CH/S=0.4 and CH/S=1.0, there is an inconsistent trend which may be caused by some errors during the mixing and casting process, i.e. porosity, dimensional shrinkage, or non-homogeneous water content in the slurry.

Fig. 2 shows Ca(OH)₂-SiO₂ mixtures with the addition of metakaolin and CaO both perform increases in compressive strength as the wt. % of addition increases. However, there is a significant increase in compressive strength after the addition of metakaolin into Ca(OH)₂-SiO₂ mixtures. The mixture of Ca(OH)₂-SiO₂ with the addition of metakaolin can form a solid mass with higher cementing properties.

Fig. 1. Compressive strength vs curing days of Ca(OH)₂-SiO₂ mixtures

Fig. 2. Compressive strength vs % addition of CaO and metakaolin in Ca(OH)₂-SiO₂ mixtures

From these results, metakaolin is a reactive pozzolan that contains SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ sites, which can react with Ca(OH)₂ in the mixture, then it is suspected that the mixture may experience a pozzolanic reaction. This result should be further confirmed by using XRD characterization to identify the phases. Whereas, the addition of CaO

into the mixture shows a slight increase in the compressive strength value along with the composition of CaO added. It has no significant effect at all due to CaO will react soon with H₂O, resulting in Ca(OH)₂, which has a low cementing ability.

5. 2. Compressive strength of the Ca(OH)₂-metakaolin-gypsum hydrated products

The compressive strength of the specimens with 41 wt. % Ca(OH)₂ – 41 wt. % metakaolin – 18 wt. % gypsum at two different curing temperatures is shown in Fig. 3. It is shown that the mixture forms a solid mass and there is an increase in the compressive strength value of the hydrated products as the curing time increases.

Fig. 3. Compressive strength vs curing time of specimens of 41 wt. % Ca(OH)₂ – 41 wt. % metakaolin – 18 wt. % gypsum with water immersed curing method at temperatures of 50 °C and 20 °C

The specimen shows a significant increase in compressive strength, indicating the formation of solid mass in the specimen due to the pozzolanic reaction. This result should be also further confirmed by using XRD characterization to identify the phases. Compared to the Ordinary Portland cement, its hydration product can have a compressive strength value of up to 33–53 MPa at 28 days of atmospheric curing. In addition, [17] explains that the water immersed curing method also supports the hydration reaction of the mixture that improves the pore structure and decreases the porosity level of the products. Besides, specimens with a curing temperature of 50 °C have a more significant increase in compressive strength than with 20 °C. It is also shown in [18] that curing temperature plays a role in the kinetics of the hydration reaction of cementitious materials. Thus, the water immersed curing method with a temperature of 50 °C has a higher kinetics or reaction rate than with 20 °C, resulting in a faster reaction and more hydration products.

5. 3. XRD characterization of the Ca(OH)₂-SiO₂ and Ca(OH)₂-metakaolin-gypsum hydrated products

The specimens with the highest compressive strength of CH-MK-G-50, CH-MK-G-20, and CH-15MK/S were characterized using the XRD method. The phase composition contained in samples CH-MK-G-50 and CH-MK-G-20 is shown in Table 2. Whereas the diffractograms are shown in Fig. 4.

Table 2

Phase composition identified by XRD on samples CH-MK-G-50 and CH-MK-G-20

Sample code	Compressive strength (28 days curing), MPa	Phase identified				
		Crystal-line CSH	Ettringite	Calcite	Quartz	Portlandite
CH-MK-G-50	22.17	23.4 %	60 %	12 %	4.6 %	–
CH-MK-G-20	6.13	30.4 %	40.2 %	19 %	2.9 %	5.6 %

Fig. 4. Diffractogram of CH-MK-G-50, CH-MK-G-20, MK, and CH-15MK/S: E – ettringite; C – calcite; Q – quartz; c-CSH – crystalline CSH; P – portlandite

Ettringite ($\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3(\text{OH})_{12}\cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and crystalline-CSH (sheet PDF-33-0306) [19] phases were only identified in both samples CH-MK-G50 and CH-MK-G-20.

The presence of ettringite was caused by the reaction between $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, Al_2O_3 sites of metakaolin, gypsum, and water. The formation of ettringite has a role to speed up the strength development at the earlier period of the specimens, like so in Portland cement hydration [6, 8]. So that, the specimens can maintain their shapes while they were immersed and cured in the water after the demoulding process.

The presence of crystalline-CSH was caused by the reaction between $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, SiO_2 site of metakaolin, and water [6]. It has the main contribution to the long-term strength of the products. Meanwhile, in Portland cement hydration, CSH is obtained from the reaction between calcium-silicates (in the cement powder) with water. Actually, the formation of CSH in Portland cement occurs in two steps of hydration [10] as mentioned in equations (1) and (2). The first hydration is calcium silicates react with water, yielding CSH_1 and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ as a side product. Then, the side product can continue to react with reactive silica compounds with the presence of the water yielding CSH_2 , which is known as secondary hydration. The secondary hydration is also called as a pozzolanic reaction. However, some literature sources state that the product of the pozzolanic reaction is not limited only to CSH, but also ettringite or CASH (calcium-aluminate-silicate-hydrate), and CAH (calcium-aluminate-hydrate) [6, 9, 12]. Therefore, from this theory and presented results, samples CH-MK-G-50 and CH-MK-G-20 experienced pozzolanic reaction due to the presence of ettringite and crystalline-CSH. They give strong binding properties to the specimens. Associated with that, sample CH-15MK/S did not experience any pozzolanic reaction. This result confirms its compressive strength value that the low binding strength of the CH-15MK/S specimen comes from the only adhesion bonding.

Portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) was identified in both samples CH-MK-G-20 and CH-15MK/S. In sample CH-MK-G-20, the presence of portlandite was due to a pozzolanic reaction that did not completely occur yet. That is because according to the reaction (2), the pozzolanic reaction needs to consume portlandite to yield CSH. Whereas in sample CH-15MK/S that did not undergo pozzolanic reaction, portlandite was surely identified. However, it may undergo a carbonation reaction due to the presence of CO_2 in the solution, so that it also contributes to the formation of calcium carbonate or calcite (CaCO_3) in the specimens [9, 20].

Fig. 6. Polarizing optical microscope examination of samples by using: *a* – parallel nicols (sample CH-MK-G-50); *b* – crossed nicols (sample CH-MK-G-50); *c*, *e* – parallel nicols (sample CH-MK-G-20); *d*, *f* – crossed nicols (sample CH-MK-G-20); E – ettringite; C – calcite; Q – quartz

Fig. 7. Portlandite grains in sample CH-MK-G-20 identified by: *a* – parallel nicol; *b* – crossed nicols with different location. The binder dissolves the surface of the portlandite grains indicating that the reaction occurs in that area

Fig. 8. Visual comparison of the images of both samples: *a*, *b*, *c* – CH-MK-G-50; *d*, *e*, *f* – CH-MK-G-20. The black granular aggregates are observed in sample CH-MK-G-20

6. Discussion of the results of the testing and characterization of the alternative low-energy binders

The compressive strength of the hydrated products of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ with or without the addition of CaO was around 0.55 MPa (Fig. 1), whereas the compressive strength of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ with the addition of metakaolin was about 2.66 MPa (Fig. 2). The hydrated products that consist of 41 wt. % of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ – 41 wt. % of metakaolin and 18 wt. % of gypsum have higher compressive strength compared to $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$, those are 22.17 MPa and 6.13 MPa in 28 days of curing (Fig. 3). XRD characterization and polarizing OM examination confirmed the compressive strength value of CH-MK-G-50 and CH-MK-G-20 underwent pozzolanic reaction due to the presence of ettringite, crystalline-CSH (Table 2) and amorphous phases (Fig. 8). The presence of the amorphous phase is characterized by the diffractograms hump (Fig. 4), and the dark color in crossed nicol examination is due to the isotropic properties of the structure shown by the polarised microscope. Besides that, the presence of ettringite phase in the specimens of 41 wt. % of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ – 41 wt. % of metakaolin and 18 wt. % of gypsum mixtures prevents them from being broken when they were immersed in water for curing. During the initial strength development of the hydrated products, ettringite, crystalline-CSH and amorphous phase act as a strong binder. Whereas calcite, quartz (Fig. 6), and some portions of portlandite (Fig. 7) act as a filler.

The results revealed one of the developments of an alternative binder to Portland cement. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and metakaolin are mainly used in this study. The calcination temperature of limestone at 1,100 °C and kaolinite clay at 750 °C used lower energy than clinkering temperature of Portland cement, which is around 1,500 °C. In the 21st century, the main focus of the building and construction industries is lowering the energy binder production and costs, and also using more eco-friendly resources. [27] shows fly ash-based geopolymer concrete with certain molarity of NaOH can obtain compressive strength of 29.34 MPa in 28 days of atmospheric curing method. [28] presents that by determining the hydraulic activity of SCMs, it can influence the technological, mechanical, and chemical properties of the low-emission multi-component cement. It is shown that combining super-zeolite (SZ) and separated fly ash (SFA) can reduce power consumption for the preparation of highly active SCMs up to 31 kWh/tonne. Another idea comes from [29] on designing an alternative alkali-activated Portland cement by using a mineral additive of granulated blast furnace slag and fly ash. The aim of the research is to accomplish the blended cement composition, in which the hydrated products can reach a higher strength than 40 MPa.

This study still uses the water immersion curing method at a certain temperature to obtain the highest compressive strength value. Whereas the study [6] used acetone to stop the hydration reaction after the curing process. Future development should be undertaken for atmospheric curing related to technical and practical applications. The hydration product of Ordinary Portland cement has a compressive strength value of about 33–53 MPa in 28 days of atmospheric curing.

It should be noted that XRD characterization provides qualitative and semi-quantitative analysis for the crystalline phase. Indeed, quantitative XRD analysis for the amorphous phase in cementitious materials also has also been developed [23, 30, 31]. Hence, for further development, it can roughly estimate the comparison between crystalline and amorphous phases that dominantly contribute to the strength of the hydrated binders.

Some development should be further undertaken in this research scope of alkali-activated cements. For example, by varying binder compositions, or developing quaternary mixtures consisting of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-metakaolin-gypsum}$ combined with other elements such as blast furnace slag, fly ash and silica fume.

7. Conclusions

1. The mixtures of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ with the addition of CaO and metakaolin did not undergo a pozzolanic reaction. The compressive strength of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ with or without the addition of CaO was around 0.55 MPa. While $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2\text{-SiO}_2$ with the addition of metakaolin showed a value of about 2.66 MPa and as confirmed by XRD this mixture did not undergo pozzolanic reaction as no CSH or ettringite phases were identified.

2. The mixtures of 41 wt. % $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ – 41 wt. % metakaolin – 18 wt. % gypsum with 28-days water immersion curing at temperatures of 50 °C and 20 °C have an average compressive strength value of 22.17 MPa and 6.13 MPa, respectively. The compressive strength showed a significant increase for the mixture that was water-cured at 50 °C for 28 days. Both treatments underwent pozzolanic reaction as shown by the presence of CSH and ettringite phases as confirmed by XRD.

3. From XRD characterization, CH-MK-G-50 mainly contains ettringite and crystalline CSH. While CH-MK-G-20 mainly contains ettringite, crystalline – CSH, with some portions of portlandite. Both diffractograms exhibit a hump at the 2θ of 20° to 40°, indicating the presence of amorphous phases.

4. The examination using a polarizing optical microscope confirmed the presence of amorphous phases indicated by a darker color feature of the microstructure. Sample CH-MK-G-50 has a denser and darker color in visual observation compared to sample CH-MK-G-20, indicating that it has more portions of the amorphous phase. The amorphous phase is suspected to be CSH gels. Other phases such as ettringite, calcite, quartz, and portlandite were also observed. It is concluded that ettringite, crystalline-CSH, and the amorphous phases act as a strong binder, while calcite, quartz, and portlandite act as fillers. All of them together contributed to the compressive strength of the mixture.

Acknowledgments

This research is self and partially funded by the Faculty of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Bandung Institute of Technology, Bandung, Indonesia.

References

1. Bye, G. C. (1999). Portland cement: composition, production and properties. Thomas Telford Ltd. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1680/pccpap.27664>
2. Taylor, H. F. W. (1997). Cement chemistry. Thomas Telford Ltd. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1680/cc.25929>

3. Flatt, R. J., Roussel, N., Cheeseman, C. R. (2012). Concrete: An eco material that needs to be improved. *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 32 (11), 2787–2798. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2011.11.012>
4. Rado, P. (1988). An introduction to the technology of pottery. Institute of Ceramics by Pergamon Press, 266.
5. Shi, C., Jiménez, A. F., Palomo, A. (2011). New cements for the 21st century: The pursuit of an alternative to Portland cement. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 41 (7), 750–763. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2011.03.016>
6. Žemlička, M., Kuzielova, E., Kuliffayova, M., Tkacz, J., Palou, M. T. (2015). Study of hydration products in the model systems metakaolin–lime and metakaolin–lime–gypsum. *Ceramics – Silik ty*, 59 (4), 283–291. Available at: https://www.ceramics-silikaty.cz/2015/pdf/2015_04_283.pdf
7. Morsy, M. S., Alsayed, S. H., Salloum, Y. A. (2012). Development of eco-friendly binder using metakaolin–fly ash–lime–anhydrous gypsum. *Construction and Building Materials*, 35, 772–777. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2012.04.142>
8. Bhanumathidas, N., Kalidas, N. (2004). Dual role of gypsum: Set retarder and strength accelerator. *Indian Concrete Journal*, 78 (3), 170–173. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/287679112_Dual_role_of_gypsum_Set_retarder_and_strength_accelerator
9. Nežerka, V., Slížková, Z., Tesárek, P., Plachý, T., Frankeová, D., Petráňová, V. (2014). Comprehensive study on mechanical properties of lime-based pastes with additions of metakaolin and brick dust. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 64, 17–29. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2014.06.006>
10. Siegesmund, S., Snethlage, R. (Eds.) (2011). *Stone in architecture: properties, durability*. Springer, 552. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-14475-2>
11. Khatib, J. M., Baalbaki, O., Elkordi, A. A. (2018). Metakaolin. *Waste and Supplementary Cementitious Materials in Concrete*, 493–511. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-08-102156-9.00015-8>
12. Rahhal, V., Talero, R. (2014). Very early age detection of ettringite from pozzolan origin. *Construction and Building Materials*, 53, 674–679. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2013.10.082>
13. Kovalchuk, O., Gelevera, O., Ivanychko, V. (2019). Studying the influence of metakaolin on self-healing processes in the contact-zone structure of concretes based on the alkali-activated Portland cement. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, 5 (6 (101)), 33–40. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2019.181501>
14. Alonso, S., Palomo, A. (2001). Alkaline activation of metakaolin and calcium hydroxide mixtures: influence of temperature, activator concentration and solids ratio. *Materials Letters*, 47 (1–2), 55–62. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-577x\(00\)00212-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-577x(00)00212-3)
15. French, W. J. (1991). Concrete petrography: a review. *Quarterly Journal of Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology*, 24 (1), 17–48. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1144/gsl.qjeg.1991.024.01.03>
16. Reedy, C. L. (2006). Review of Digital Image Analysis of Petrographic Thin Sections in Conservation Research. *Journal of the American Institute for Conservation*, 45 (2), 127–146. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1179/019713606806112531>
17. James, T., Malachi, A., Gadzama, E. W., Anamtemok, A. (2011). Effect of curing methods on the compressive strength of concrete. *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, 30 (3), 14–20. Available at: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/njt/article/view/123538>
18. Narmluk, M., Nawa, T. (2014). Effect of Curing Temperature on Pozzolanic Reaction of Fly Ash in Blended Cement Paste. *International Journal of Chemical Engineering and Applications*, 5 (1), 31–35. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7763/ijcea.2014.v5.346>
19. Jumate, E., Manea, D. L. (2011). X-ray diffraction study of hydration processes in the Portland cement. *Journal of Applied Engineering Science*, 1 (1), 79–86. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/file.PostFileLoader.html?id=54c14753d2fd6445588b45b8&assetKey=AS%3A273678338592769%401442261409008>
20. Šavija, B., Luković, M. (2016). Carbonation of cement paste: Understanding, challenges, and opportunities. *Construction and Building Materials*, 117, 285–301. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.04.138>
21. Matschei, T., Lothenbach, B., Glasser, F. P. (2007). The role of calcium carbonate in cement hydration. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 37 (4), 551–558. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2006.10.013>
22. Bergold, S. T., Goetz-Neunhoeffler, F., Neubauer, J. (2013). Quantitative analysis of C–S–H in hydrating alite pastes by in-situ XRD. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 53, 119–126. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2013.06.001>
23. Bhagath Singh, G. V. P., Subramaniam, K. V. L. (2016). Quantitative XRD Analysis of Binary Blends of Siliceous Fly Ash and Hydrated Cement. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 28 (8), 04016042. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)mt.1943-5533.0001554](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)mt.1943-5533.0001554)
24. Hunnicutt, W. A. (2013). Characterization of calcium-silicate-hydrate and calcium-alumino-silicate-hydrate. Urbana, Illinois. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/16750866.pdf>
25. Fabbri, B., Gualtieri, S., Shoal, S. (2014). The presence of calcite in archeological ceramics. *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 34 (7), 1899–1911. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2014.01.007>
26. Lukschová, Š., Příkryl, R., Pertold, Z. (2009). Petrographic identification of alkali–silica reactive aggregates in concrete from 20th century bridges. *Construction and Building Materials*, 23 (2), 734–741. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2008.02.020>
27. Herwani, Pane, I., Imran, I., Budiono, B. (2018). Compressive Strength of Fly ash-based Geopolymer Concrete with a Variable of Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH) Solution Molarity. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 147, 01004. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201814701004>
28. Ivashchyshyn, H., Sanytsky, M., Kropyvnytska, T., Rusyn, B. (2019). Study of low-emission multi-component cements with a high content of supplementary cementitious materials. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, 4 (6 (100)), 39–47. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2019.175472>
29. Krivenko, P., Petropavlovskiy, O., Kovalchuk, O., Lapovska, S., Pasko, A. (2018). Design of the composition of alkali activated portland cement using mineral additives of technogenic origin. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, 4 (6 (94)), 6–15. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2018.140324>
30. Bhagath Singh, G. V. P., Subramaniam, K. V. L. (2016). Quantitative XRD study of amorphous phase in alkali activated low calcium siliceous fly ash. *Construction and Building Materials*, 124, 139–147. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.07.081>
31. Suherman, P. M., van Riessen, A., O'Connor, B., Li, D., Bolton, D., Fairhurst, H. (2002). Determination of amorphous phase levels in Portland cement clinker. *Powder Diffraction*, 17 (3), 178–185. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1154/1.1471518>